

Oral presentation

A versatile mesoscale and microscale model for Titan

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Titan's weather is particularly active at all spatial scales: global (e.g., super-rotating winds), intermediate / mesoscale (e.g., convective thunderstorms, air-sea circulations), local (e.g., turbulence in the planetary boundary layer, the atmospheric layer in direct contact with the surface). The end of the Cassini mission in 2017 and the prospective of the Dragonfly launch in 2027 lead us to formulate open questions on the mechanisms underlying the atmospheric phenomena unveiled by Cassini and Huygens: (Q1) How the Titan wind variability is characterized at the mesoscale and the local scales, under the influence of turbulence, topography and methane storms? (Q2) What makes Titan's aeolian environment so active, in particular at the dune fields? What are the aerosols and volatiles exchanges between the surface and the atmosphere? (Q3) In which atmospheric environment the flying quadcopter of the Dragonfly mission will evolve? How to prepare its atmospheric measurements to maximize the science return of the mission?

The main tools developed to study Titan's weather are global-climate models (GCM) in which mesh spacing is coarse, allowing to address large-scale circulations and Titan's climate variability. The existing body of work of fine-scale atmospheric modeling for Titan, albeit extremely successful, rely on a paradigm in which one particular ad-hoc mesoscale model is used for a given particular phenomenon: the dynamics of Titan's methane thunderstorms have been assessed by either high-resolution idealized three-dimensional models, or two-dimensional models with detailed cloud microphysics; the rich atmospheric dynamics close to Titan lakes has also been unveiled by detailed, modeling studies. The community is at a turning point where the next step is to build versatile mesoscale modeling approach to tackle several questions at the same time and to be capable of addressing future, yet unknown, challenges.

To draw a line beyond this turning point and to address questions Q1 Q2 Q3, we aim to develop a new limited-area model for Titan based a coupling of the Weather Research and Forecast dynamical core with the Titan physical packages (e.g., radiative transfer, cloud microphysics) developed for the LMD Titan Planetary Climate Model. We will apply this model to explore three topics in Titan's meteorology: (T1) turbulence in Titan's planetary boundary layer, with large-eddy simulations; (T2) regional wind systems and aeolian erosion, with mesoscale simulations including realistic topography; (T3) methane storms and their link to the methane cycle, with idealized and realistic cloud-resolving simulations. At the workshop, results from the first topic will be presented and perspectives on research and methodology on the second and third topics will be detailed.